

Task 2.4 report: An ex-post study of successful innovation processes and best practices regarding SFT development

Maria Kernecker, Andrea Knierim, Teresa Kraus,
Friederike Borges, Angelika Wurbs

Müncheberg, June 2018

smartAKIS
Smart Farming Thematic Network

Document Summary

Deliverable Title: Report on successful innovation processes and best practices around SFT

Version: 1

Deliverable Lead: ZALF

Related Work package: 2

Author(s): Maria Kernecker, Andrea Knierim, Teresa Kraus, Friederike Borges, Angelika Wurbs

Contributor(s):

Reviewer(s): Thanos Balafoutis, Spyros Fountas

Communication level:

- PU Public

- PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

- RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

- CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Grant Agreement Number: 696294

Project name: SMART AKIS

Start date of Project: March 2016

Duration: 30 months

Project coordinator: Agricultural University of Athens

Executive Summary

In order to develop a comprehensive understanding of SFT innovation systems and processes, we analysed successful innovations, by starting our analysis with the felt need and the origins of the innovative idea, through to its implementation and diffusion. Six examples of appropriate cases were chosen in close collaboration with the practice partners of Smart-AKIS (AUA, ACTA, INTIA, ZALF and Delphy) and interactively studied the innovation processes by closely looking at key actors and their functions, and key events. We received three case studies of innovative products (trecker.com, agrivi, and arable smart sprayer) and three case studies of innovative practices (CTF in both Spain and The UK, and section controlled spraying in The Netherlands). Collaborations between innovators and farmers were key interactions throughout all phases of all innovations, and were a key supporting factor. Other supporting factors for the success of the innovations included demonstrations and field days, motivation and positive attitudes of the innovators. Hindering factors were funding at different point, technology availability and compatibility, and infrastructure.

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1 Introduction and conceptual background

Development shifts from mechanical to digital farm tools and machinery have broadened the spectrum of actors who are involved in agricultural innovation processes, and simultaneously have increased the variety of potentially interconnected tools and technologies. Recent technological developments are diverse and encompass (1) managing spatial and temporal variability for reducing environmental impacts of farming through precision agriculture (Suprem et al., 2013); (2) applying farm management information systems for managing data to support farm operations and functions (Fountas et al., 2015); and (3) using automated systems, robotics, and artificial intelligence at all levels of agricultural production (Zhang and Kovacs, 2012). Together, these technological innovations can be described as “Smart Farming Technologies” (SFT). While they may not yet be widespread throughout Europe, SFT are beginning to replace or complement traditional farming tools and practices. We consider these technological changes as examples for digital innovations that merit in-depth analysis in order to better understand fostering and hindering factors driving such processes. Here, we present a study that explores 6 SFT innovation cases in the frame of the EU-funded smart-AKIS project.

How common farm tools or practices are replaced with SFT depends on the innovation’s characteristics, farmers and farm related factors, and determining characteristics of the innovation system and its (institutional) environment at several contextual levels. Accordingly, we differentiate between a static picture of the multitude of (possibly) influencing facts, which we call the structural perspective, and the procedural view of an innovation creation and diffusion process. The latter addresses change over time and which we call the dynamic perspective. The structural perspective of innovations – in this case, SFT – highlights innovations as a result of actors collaborating in specific organisational structures and with sets of capacities with the aim to bring about change that improves a situation considerably, all of which occurs within certain social, political, or national environments (Fig. 1). As such, the space in which innovations are developed responds to multiple, overlapping factors.

Figure 1 Structural perspective of where innovations occur (Knierim et al. 2015)

An innovation can also be described by the process of change that occurs over time in which an innovation develops. To describe this change-process, a three-stages model of voluntary change of behavior was developed by Lewin (1947), highlighting fostering and hindering forces of innovations. As the adoption of technology, policies, or social structures is likely the result of numerous factors, all of which change over time (Darnhofer, 2014), we propose a modified model to reflect a dynamic multi-actor setting (Fig 2) (Knierim et al. 2015). More specifically, the innovation process embodies complex interdependencies and interactions between actors who are shaped by influences from their changing environment. The role of stakeholders and various actors such as agricultural services supply agencies, distribution partners, input suppliers, universities and research institutes, and companies in providing information, sharing knowledge and supporting innovation has been captured in models such as the AKIS framework (Oreszczyn et al., 2010). Understanding both the environment in which innovation occurs, and the interactions that make up innovation processes, can provide insights to SFT development so that the innovation process is inclusive, appropriate, and relevant to farms and farmers at different levels (EU SCAR 2012), therefore in support of a resilient European agricultural and rural landscape.

To better understand the interactions that constitute innovation processes, it is key to closely explore the organizations and actors involved in innovations, specifically the links and interactions between them, and the institutional infrastructure at play. Because social interactions (e.g. cooperation, networking) build knowledge that ultimately leads to successful innovations (Klerkx and Leeuwis, 2009), innovation is a social process with at least a strong bottom-up component rather than top-down intervention (EU SCAR, 2012). Networking between actors is considered important to innovations' success, including entrepreneurs, researchers and advisors (Smits, 2010). These actors can bring new products, new processes, and new forms of organization into economic use, together with the institutions and policies that affect the way knowledge is shared, accessed, and used (Leeuwis and van den Ban, 2004). Successful innovations are often the result of synergy among three configuration spheres: the technical, organizational and institutional one. In a similar sense, Leeuwis and Aarts (2011) highlight that innovations are a combined implementation of new technologies and practices (hardware), new knowledge and ways of thinking software) and new institutions or organization (orgware). Hence, innovations can be considered as sociotechnical hybrids (Flichy 2008).

Figure 2 Dynamic perspective of innovation processes (Knierim et al., 2015).

Successful innovation processes in agriculture have been studied in manifold ways. One prominent conceptual result is the 'diffusion of innovation' curve that differentiates actors within a social system according to the moment they actually adopt the innovation (Rogers 2003). The resulting terminology (early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards) has been criticised as semantically distorted and pejorative (for the laggards) (Hoffmann 2007). As a less normatively prescriptive model, we propose to use a modified diffusion of innovation curve (Fig 3, Hoffmann et al. 2009). The adoption of an innovation occurs when a member of a social group perceives a problem and applies a change. The innovator is the first person to practice an innovation within a certain social system, and has to modify their behavior in order to accomplish the change. Most often, innovations are adopted by distinct individuals but the innovation is not disseminated widely throughout the social system (Hoffmann, et al., 2009). Diffusion of an innovation occurs when it is disseminated throughout the social system, taking into account the role of information, risk, and the social position of the farmers (Darnhofer, 2014). The rate at which farmers adopt an innovation can serve as an indicator of the effectiveness of the innovation and its appropriateness to end users' needs or context (Hoffmann, et al., 2009).

Figure 3: Diffusion curve with four key stages (Hoffman et al., 2009:97, complemented)

Looking closer at the innovation itself to better understand the technical dimension, there are five characteristics– as perceived by individuals – that may function as fostering or hindering factor and impact on the rate of innovation adoption: (1) Relative advantage is how much better an innovation is perceived to be compared to the preceding idea, technology, or method; (2) Compatibility describes how much an innovation is perceived as being consistent with values, past experiences, and needs of potential adopters. If an idea is incompatible, it won't be adopted as quickly; (3) Complexity reflects how difficult to understand and use an innovation is. The more complicated an innovation is, the more slowly it is to be adopted; (4) Triability is the degree to which an innovation may be experimented with and then adopted on an incremental basis, rather than all at once. This serves as a sort of insurance; (5) Observability is the degree to which the outcome of an innovation is visible to others. If results are easily visible, then the innovation is more likely to be adopted (Rogers, 2003). Thus, an innovation's diffusion can be partially explained with these characteristics.

Given the wide range of SFT, the different stages of their development, and their not yet comprehensively confirmed relevance for the sector, we wanted to explore and assess factors determining success of innovation processes of different SFT types. Here, we present 6 innovations, whose development processes make them “success stories” and analyse them according to a) the key actors with structural and capacity related characteristics, and b) fostering and hindering events and environmental conditions in the course of the innovation process. To systematically study and reflect on these innovation cases, we used the timeline analysis methodology, also frequently referred to as event analysis or historical timeline analysis which will be presented in the next section.

2 Methods

The smart-AKIS innovation case study was conducted as a parallel and comparative cases' study, realised by six research teams in six countries, and methodologically guided by the ZALF team.

2.1 Methodological approach

A case study approach is a research method described as an “in-depth description and analysis of a bounded system” (Merriam, 2009:40). The most important feature is the object of the study, and the resulting product should be both or either descriptive and empirical in nature (Stake, 1995). By doing a comparative, qualitative analysis of selected successful innovation processes, we aim to identify best practices for SFT development.

2.2 Methodological procedure

There were 6 project partners/hubs in smart-AKIS that were each responsible for a case study on successful SFT innovations. Over the course of approximately 4 months, each of the partners used the methods that the ZALF team prescribed to collect data for their case study (Table 1). The project partners then put all information together into a report, which contained a graphical timeline. The methods that project partners used to collect data are detailed below.

Table 1 Overview of which project partners from which countries conducted case studies on distinct innovations.

Country	Innovation	Brief description
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Germany	trecker.com	Farm Management and Information System
Greece	Arable Smart Sprayer	Variable Rate Technology App?
Serbia/Croatia	Agrivi	Farm Management and Information System
Spain	Automatic guiding of agricultural machinery	Controlled Traffic Farming
Netherlands	Section control on sprayers with use of GPS	Variable Rate Technology
UK	Controlled Traffic Farming using permanent traffic-lanes	Controlled Traffic Farming

2.2.1 Case study selection

Innovation case studies were selected and proposed by project partners. Project partners proposed innovations that fit the cause using a profile pattern which was jointly agreed upon and tested in advance (see Annex I). Next, the proposals were screened, assessed and filtered by a committee comprised of representatives of project coordination, research, machinery/industry, farmers and advisory services applying selection criteria as stated in an assessment scheme (see Annex II). Six case studies were selected. Each of the case studies was then elaborated by project partners (both from practice and research). Each project partner was responsible for conducting the case study and learned how to do so using the timeline analysis methodology at a training workshop that was held by ZALF project partners in Berlin, October 2017.

2.2.2 Conducting the case studies

We used the timeline analysis methodology for conducting our retrospective (ex-post) study (Hekkert and Negro, 2009; Klerkx et al., 2012; Reichardt et al., 2016). The timeline analysis method allowed our project partners to document and understand the key stages of an innovation process, specifically, which actors were involved at which points and what they did (Eastwood et al., 2016). Basically, key events, activities or changes are displayed chronologically in order to trace the innovation process. A graphical timeline was complemented with a text description that included all relevant data.

The activities and events that comprised the phases of an innovation process were allocated to three phases: the initiation phase, the implementation phase, and the diffusion phase. In the initiation phase, a problem is manifesting and farmers/stakeholders feel the need to change something in the farming process to overcome the challenge. An idea for an innovation is taken up, operationalized, and potential partners are sought out. Next, in the implementation phase, the plan turns into action. The innovation is now accessible to other stakeholders who consider themselves in a similar situation as the innovator. Coming from a technology provider's side, the innovation is at this point being published and marketed. Finally, in the diffusion phase, the innovation is accepted. Thinking of a problem, the innovation pops up as a possible solution. This means that the critical phase has been overcome and the innovation has gained significant attention by the public (cf. Fig. 3, page 7).

Data for the timeline was drawn from various sources. The collection of data relied on three methods. First, the analysis of existing documents, including articles in scientific journals, trade magazines, local newspapers, accessible 'grey' documents (e.g. reports), commercials, online materials including - among others - youtube videos, and audio clips. Second, interactive stakeholder meetings provided project partners with the opportunity to document the stakeholders' views and memories. Such meetings could have any type of format, including gathering stakeholders in a field day, workshop, or similar event revolving around the innovation process related to the case study. Interactive group events have the advantage of mutual stimulation and activation of memories. Third, given the time constraints facing project partners, they may have conducted or complemented the data collection with bilateral interviews.

The data that was collected was then used to elaborate the timeline visualizing the chronological course of events and activities, divided into phases (initiation, implementation, diffusion), and involved stakeholders. The degree of detail strongly depended on the available and accessible data to feed the timeline with. The activities and stakeholders that appeared in the timeline depended largely upon the case study focus and the importance of the influencing event or actor. Any activity or event affecting the innovation process was accounted for in the timeline. Stakeholders were considered as any actors influencing the innovation process, such as farmers, agricultural services supply agencies, advisory services distribution partners, input suppliers, universities and research institutes, companies, funding authorities or other organisations sharing knowledge or resources to support the innovation.

2.2.3 Data analysis

Each project partner submitted their case study report where they presented their findings in text form, and also included a graphical representation of the timeline. The text addressed key actors and events in each of the three phases of the innovation process. Subsequently, we read through each of the reports and used an open coding technique (comparable to annotation, see Newing 2011) to analyse the text and identify the key actors. Our coding helped us to identify similarities and differences throughout the case studies. We coded case studies according to the innovation phases (initiation, implementation, diffusion) and key actors, and key attributes, drivers and hindrances. Drivers could broadly be grouped into supporting factors, including social, technical, regulatory/political, and financial support. Hindrances could be broadly grouped into social, technical, financial, or even political/infrastructure barriers. We identified a total of 14 actor categories that were active throughout the innovation processes.

Table 2 Actor categories used to analyse case studies.

Actor category	Description
1. Farmer	Can act as the collaborator in developing innovation, can provide training to innovators, can be the targeted end-user, or can also act as contractor
2. Researcher	Can act as collaborator in the innovation process
3. Advisor	Can act as collaborator in the innovation process, or as the multiplier and information provider regarding the innovation
4. IT experts	Can act as the innovator or the collaborator
5. Competitor	Similar product
6. Marketer	Position within company or an outsourced company

	seeking to market and expand market for the innovation
7. Media	Press, social media, attention from wider group of people
8. Professional association	Professional networks for similar interests. Professional network includes the founders2be or the entrepreneurial support network
9. Funding organisation (public, private, venture capital)	Where the funding comes from (EU projects, private trusts/endowments, venture capital investments)
10. Public authority	Decision-makers at regional levels, policy decisions, etc.
11. Infrastructure provider	Actor responsible for installing / implementing / disseminating GPS, broadband, GNSS, RTK, can be private or public provider depending on the context.
12. Agri-tech manufacturer	Manufacturer of SFT or innovation
13. Agri-tech provider	Intermediate actor between innovation manufacturer and enduser
14. Private actor	Friend, family

3 Case studies

In the following sub-sections, we present the six case studies, which were conducted by the project partners. The description of the cases is based on reports elaborated in close collaboration between project partners and innovators and/or other contact persons familiar with the innovation at stake. For each case, we present a brief summary of the case (innovation profile), then we highlight actors and activities as revealed per phase (initiation, implementation and dissemination) and finally, compile key attributes, drivers and hindrances.

For the sake of consistency of the cases, we present partly paraphrased and condensed versions of each case study that still contain all relevant information. To distinguish paraphrases from direct quotations (as written in the reports) the latter are presented in italics. Each report can be downloaded from the smart-AKIS website (www.smart-akis.com).

3.1 trecker.com (GER)

Innovation Profile

Trecker.com is a *cloud-based farm management software solution that captures and documents information via smartphone while working on the field*. The app processes automatically collected data on tasks, working time, costs, machines, supplies etc. into *precise key figures for farmers' costs and revenues*. All data regarding finished tasks, incurred costs and working hours are automatically transferred to the acreage index. Farmers can also use software to create tasks, assign them to specific employees, and select fields, machines and resources.

Innovation process and timeline

Figure 4: Timeline of Trecker.com

Initiation Phase

The founders of trecker.com (IT EXPERTS) became acquainted via an online founder platform in 2012. A personal contact at the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (PRIVATE ACTOR) motivated the founders to *develop farming software*. Not having had any experience in the agricultural sector, the founders spent *several months as trainees on different farms* (FARMER) to learn about farming processes. The founders observed that agricultural machinery was technically advanced, but that farmers (FARMER) nevertheless struggled with time-consuming management processes. The founders thus decided to *develop software to simplify these processes*. Throughout the development, contractors (FARMER) were involved to give feedback to improve the software. *In autumn 2013 the first version of the management software was introduced and tested by collaborating contractors* (FARMER).

Implementation phase

In 2014, the founders (IT EXPERTS) received substantial financial aid from a venture capital investor (PRIVATE FUNDING ORGANISATION) so trecker.com could fund the development of new features. Trecker.com also participated in a contest for digital innovations and was one of the ten finalists (MEDIA).

Dissemination phase

In 2015, trecker.com published their *cloud based management software for farmers* which attracted attention at *AGRITECHNICA 2015* (MEDIA). At the fair, *365FarmNet* (COMPETITOR), warned trecker.com *regarding their advertisement*, since 365FarmNet perceived conflict of interest due to advertising message. By changing the tecker.com banner

to avoid possible violations of any regulation, the innovation received significant attention by the media (MEDIA), such that 365FarmNet’s commentary ultimately contributed positively to trecker.com’s publicity. In 2016 trecker.com became a *member of the entrepreneurs’ organization*, an exclusive alliance of companies (PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION). In 2017, *trecker.com received funding* by the EU (PUBLIC FUNDING ORGANIZATION) for the project “*Big Data Agrarplattform*”, with which *new features and functions, such as satellite and weather data*, were planned to be *integrated*. Between 2015 and 2017, *media response – online as well as in journals, newspaper, etc., articles, interviews and recommendations for the app – increased significantly* and provided more public visibility for the company (MEDIA).

Key attributes, drivers and hindrances

Although none of the founders were related to agriculture, they were able to develop a successful solution for farmers to better *handle their farm management processes*. *Within this whole innovation process they worked very closely with several farmers/contractors, asked the right questions and gained trust and encouragement by starting from scratch*. Despite being limited in terms of financial resources and other issues, the founders *kept going and stayed positive*. From the perspective of the founders, having a customer service orientation is the key to developing a successful product. A “*learning by doing*” attitude, free from fear of failure, and an open mind helped the founders (Wilms and Voigt) to understand the needs of farmers and translate needs into a helpful farm management tool. The founders perceive simplicity as the most important though most difficult attribute of their product. Flexibility to customize the innovation to the varying needs of the users is necessary. Sharing knowledge with other founders and *not trying to “reinvent the wheel”* are also perceived as key attributes for the success of this specific innovation process.

Table 3 Key drivers and hindrances in each innovation phase in the trecker.com innovation process

trecker.com	Drivers	Hindrances
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT expertise • Open mind for problems in agricultural production • Cooperation with farmers and contractors 	
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Company receives massive financial support by investor • Attention through awards & nominations • Publicity through dissuasion by competitor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial resources at first limited, external funding needed
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attention by media • Access to entrepreneurs organisation • Funding by EU 	

3.2 Agrivi (SER/CRO)

Innovation Profile

Agrivi is a cloud-based *farm management software* for fruit, vegetable and grain producers which refers to best farming practice knowledge. With Agrivi, farmers can *plan all seasonal activities, track their execution and related costs. Advanced reports and dashboards help farmers to make data-driven decisions needed for improving their production.* The software also integrates weather data to alert farmers about optimal times for spraying and pest control measures.

Innovation process and timeline

Figure5 Graphical timeline of the agrivi innovation process

Initiation phase

Out of ideological reasons, the founder of Agrivi (IT EXPERT) changed professions. *To learn more about agriculture, he started his own blueberry hobby farm.* Since consolidating knowledge and information on agricultural production was complicated, the founder had the *idea to develop an application that allows all farm activities to be monitored, assessed and evaluated according to operational goals of the farm.* After assessing the feasibility and commercial potential for such software in collaboration with *farmers and agronomists (FARMER), a software prototype was built and tested on the field in real-life conditions.*

Implementation Phase

By mid-2014, the founder of Agrivi (IT EXPERT) secured the first seed investment from private investors (PRIVATE FUNDING ORGANIZATION) signed the first large-scale contract with an apple grower from Croatia (FARMER). In 2014, Agrivi won first place for the best

start-up at the World Start-up Competition, for which Agrivi was awarded prize money (PRIVATE FUNDING ORGANIZATION), and consequently received global attention. This had a positive effect on the company's promotion and branding (MEDIA). In 2015, Agrivi received funding from private and public sources (PRIVATE/PUBLIC FUNDING ORGANIZATION). Agrivi was presented in three global market research reports (MEDIA). Furthermore, the Ministry of Agriculture of Alberta, Canada (PUBLIC AUTHORITY) used Agrivi as a role-model for farm management software, as did the Association of young farmers of the United States of America (PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION). In 2016, Agrivi gained further public attention by participating in various competitions and awards throughout the worldwide start-up scene. As a result, Agrivi was noticed and approached by a venture capital investor (PRIVATE FINANCING ORGANIZATION) who invested €1 million in the company. In this phase, Agrivi expanded throughout the global market and quickly increased the number of employees.

Dissemination Phase

As part of their international expansion, Agrivi targeted the agricultural market in Poland. Besides investing in advertising, the company presented the benefits of the software directly to farmers (FARMER). Also, Agrivi collaborated with one of the largest agri-technical providers in Poland, the Osadowski Group (MARKETER, FARMER). Most of the earlier acquired capital was used to develop a sales network starting with Poland, and expand into Lithuania and Latvia by relying on a partnership with a multinational agri- food company (MARKETER). Finally, Agrivi is participating in a project funded by the European Commission (PUBLIC FUNDING ORGANIZATION) that supports the process of company internationalization with individual training programs. In January 2018, Agrivi counted 40.000 users in more than 150 countries.

Key attributes, drivers and hindrances

Originally, the founder was not related to agriculture, but developed strong ideological motivation to centralize on-farm processes. The founder relied on collaboration with farmers to improve the software, and had a pro-active attitude to participate in start-up competitions. Participating in these competitions helped Agrivi gain substantial attention world-wide, and seemed to have legitimize investments by private funding organizations in addition to marketing through influential agri-tech providers in Eastern Europe.

Table 4 Key drivers and hindrances in each innovation phase of the agrivi innovation process

Agrivi	Drivers	Hindrances
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong ideological motivation of founder • IT expertise • Open mind for problems in agricultural production • Cooperation with farmers and agronomists 	

Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Company receives massive financial support by several investors • Awards & trophy money • Worldwide attention through awards and nominations • Publicity through appearance in global market reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial resources at first limited, external funding needed
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion to international markets (Poland) and cooperation with large industry partners • Support for capacity building by EU training program 	

3.3 Arable Smart Sprayer (GR)

Innovation Profile

The Arable Smart Sprayer is a web-based app to help farmers choose the *ideal spraying time* for their crops. Spraying conditions are viewed for the *selected day and/or the next three days* taking into account the current weather situation and the weather forecast. Spraying in optimal conditions helps avoiding spraying drift and resulting negative effects on the environment, improves the spraying efficiency and results in input reduction and cost savings. Recognising the crop type, crop stage and development, the type of the chemical compound, the harmful insect and/or the plant disease, and the actual weather conditions, the Arable Smart Sprayer also proposes the *optimal calibration for orchard mist blowers*. Furthermore, the app provides a *real-time indicator for the optimal forward speed of the tractor*. The speed indicator incorporates the calculation of the tractor speed to make comparisons with the optimal speed for ensuring that the farmers are spraying the optimal compound quantities.

Innovation process and timeline

Figure 6 Graphical timeline of the arable smart sprayer innovation process

Initiation phase

AGENSO, a company for agricultural and environmental solutions (Agenso company includes IT-experts), and the Agricultural Cooperative of Pella (ACP) were collaborating on another precision-agricultural project in 2015, and as a result of the collaboration, they had the idea for the Arable Smart Sprayer (AGRI-TECH PROVIDER, including IT EXPERT, ADVISOR, RESEARCHER). *Growers and agriculturalists (FARMER) within ACP identified the spraying performance as an important issue to lower production costs and environmental impacts. Subsequently, AGENSO (AGRI-TECH PROVIDER, including IT EXPERT, ADVISOR, RESEARCHER) completed the necessary research to adequately capture the idea of the "Arable Smart Sprayer".*

Implementation phase

The "Arable Smart Sprayer" software was created in 2015-2016, by AGENSO (AGRI-TECH PROVIDER, including IT EXPERT, ADVISOR, RESEARCHER), for the optimization of spraying arable and cotton crops, targeting reduced inputs. During the implementation phase, some first trials were done and modifications and enhancements were introduced. No major challenges or barriers were recorded for this specific innovation. Funding was the only issue, as the innovation was self-funded by the company. AGENSO is preparing the hardware, which will be used for enabling the sprayer's parameter modification, enabling the system to spray according to a variable rate.

Diffusion phase

The "Arable Smart Sprayer" is in the first phase of the diffusion process; a few alpha users (FARMER), members of the ACP, are using of the innovation, and evaluating the results of using the app. The system is expected to be completed by summer 2018.

Key attributes, drivers and hindrances

No major difficulties were recorded for this specific successful innovation. Funding can be the only issue. In Greece there is no competition in the farming sector, as the market demand is pretty high and the available solutions are limited, and so it is worthwhile getting involved in new innovations on this field. The collaboration between AGENSO and ACP was imperative from the beginning.

Table 5 Key drivers and hindrances in each of the innovation phases in the arable smart sprayer innovation process

Arable Smart Sprayer	Drivers	Hindrances
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cooperation with agricultural cooperative 	
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No/little competition on Greek market for smart farming technologies, but high demand 	
Dissemination		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding might be future issue

3.4 Section control in spraying (NL)

Innovation Profile

Section control in spraying is an automatic system of opening and closing nozzles and sections based on the location within the field. The system uses data on field boundaries and where the field has already been sprayed to automatically reduce the overlap of spraying tracks and outside of field boundaries. As such, this reduces the use, overdose, and drift of pesticides. The system functions autonomously and is not dependent on the driver or operator, leading to more reliable results.

Innovation process and timeline

Figure 7 Graphical timeline of the section control innovation process in the Netherlands

Initiation Phase

In 1995, an accurate GPS signal became available for Dutch farmers, which made using GPS applications possible, thereby encouraging a wider presence of GPS companies, researchers, and large tractor companies (INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER, AGRITECH MANUFACTURER, RESEARCHER) to invest in solutions based on location information, auto-steering, and controlled traffic. Accordingly, on-farm demonstrations were conducted for farmers throughout the Netherlands and at Agritechnica in Hannover in 2007 (FARMER). Moreover, the Dutch crop protection policy, which supports integrated pest management to reduce pesticide drift to the environment further promoted the development of the innovation, and specifically in drift in surface water, by passing regulation in 2001 (PUBLIC AUTHORITY). Due to the abundant water courses in the Netherlands and the high cost of land, the Dutch agri-technical community responded to the regulation by focusing on spraying technology rather than on cropping-free zones (AGRITECH PROVIDER, AGRITECH MANUFACTURER). Starting in 2004, companies developing spraying technologies focused on using section control in spraying machines (AGRITECH MANUFACTURER).

Implementation Phase

As of 2007 and 2008, in-field demonstrations (FARMER) spread information about section control in spraying (AGRITECH MANUFACTURER & PROVIDER, ADVISOR – like DLV Plant/Delphy, FARMER). Farmers' high income and need to invest in new tractors in 2009/2010 further supported the implementation of the innovation (FARMER). Farmers

bought and used tractors with auto-steering. Based on the benefits of using auto-steering, farmers requested additional solutions, including machine control (FARMER, AGRITECH MANUFACTURER).

Dissemination Phase

A number of demonstrations (Potato Europe, Agritechnica Hannover, Agricultural Technology Holland, and National Onion Field Day) of the technology from 2012 to 2014 allowed farmers to observe and experience the technology, and the ease of its use (FARMER, AGRITECH MANUFACTURER, AGRITECH PROVIDER). During this phase, the most important actors were local dealers, farm advisors and the government (AGRITECH PROVIDER, ADVISOR, PUBLIC AUTHORITY). Dutch public policy allows farmers subsidies covering up to 30% of investments in sprayers with section control (PUBLIC FUNDING ORGANIZATION), which caused farmers to buy their new sprayers during the 2012-2014 policy phase (FARMER). High farm income coming from high crop prices in those years, allows farmers to invest in new technology with GPS section control as well.

Key attributes, drivers and hindrances

The success of the innovation was made possible by the introduction of GPS within agricultural technologies for farmers, in addition to a precise GPS signal at a reasonable price. Manufacturers aimed to develop simple technology to increase GPS potential for tractors. After farmers made the initial investment in GPS and auto steering, they became interested in other applications of the GPS technology. The first users of section control on sprayers were enthusiastic from the beginning and became ambassadors of the system. Subsidies from the government stimulated farmers to buy section control on the next new sprayer. Several years with high farm income encouraged investment in section control on sprayers. Nowadays section control is a standard option on sprayers.

Table 6 Overview of the drivers and hindrances in each innovation phase of the section control spraying innovation

Section Control Spraying	Drivers	Hindrances
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agri-tech manufacturers perceive potentials, test options • Innovators' curiosity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • little experience and evidence for farmers that GPS was a solid investment • costs for the initial investment, (approximately 20000 Euro for the steering system and 18000 for an RTK GPS base station)

Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology functions fully automatic (no input on settings, dosages and agronomic knowledge is needed to have full benefits of the technology) • field demonstrations • first users and advisers were positive about using section control on sprayers and became the first ambassadors of the technology • Articles in farm journals, online and on paper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high initial investments • some farmers do not believe technology is technical reliable or dealer is not able to service and train the use of the products
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more and more satisfied users of GPS systems act as ambassador for the technology • Technology suppliers offer more and more equipment that can use GPS for precise application • Subsidies from the Dutch Government for the investment in GPS technology and equipment • Promotion activities from local dealers • Articles in farm journals, online and on papers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • initial investment rather high, (farmers are reluctant to invest in these kind of technology in years farm income is rather low, wait until the old sprayer needs to be replaced)

3.5 Controlled Traffic Farming (ES)

Innovation Profile

Controlled Traffic Farming (CTF) uses GPS and an autonomous system of driving for tractors, allowing farmers to use the same lane for cultivating in their fields. CTF decreases soil compaction and increases precision in labour and inputs (pesticides and fertilizers). Farmers thus benefit economically by saving materials (e.g. inputs, seeds). Moreover, there is a large environmental advantage for biodiversity in and around farms.

Innovation process and timeline

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Figure 8 Graphical timeline of the CTF innovation process in Spain

Initiation phase

Starting in the 1990s, CTF was introduced to farms throughout Navarre with the support of commercial machinery companies and their regional distributors, technicians of the Government of Navarre, technicians of ITG Agrícola-INTIA, and innovative farmers (AGRITECH MANUFACTURER, AGRITECH PROVIDER, PUBLIC AUTHORITY, PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION, ADVISOR, FARMER). The widespread distribution of field maps that ITG Agrícola had made based on its experimental farm in Ilundain was instrumental to spreading information about CTF (ADVISOR, FARMER). Together with technology distributors, ITG Agrícola-INTIA organized meetings and field demonstrations with the available equipment (AGRITECH PROVIDER, ADVISOR). At the same time, tractors equipped with both manual and automatic guidance became available on the market (AGRITECH MANUFACTURER, AGRITECH PROVIDER). In 2005, ITG Agrícola-INTIA participated in an European R&D project (COREA) to develop new technologies and implement them throughout rural areas (PUBLIC FUNDING, ADVISOR).

Implementation phase

While the same group of actors were involved in the implementation phase, their numbers grew (AGRITECH MANUFACTURER, AGRITECH PROVIDER, PUBLIC AUTHORITY, PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION, ADVISOR, FARMER). The Government of Navarre installed 8 RTK Stations to improve the coverage and accuracy of the GPS signal, so that it could also be used by farmers and their tractors and machines (PUBLIC

INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER, FARMER). The available technology significantly improved and was subsequently incorporated into the new tractor models as an additional offer by the manufacturers (manual guidance and automatic guidance) (AGRITECH MANUFACTURER). Together with the technology distributors, ITG Agrícola-INTIA kept organizing meetings and field demonstrations with the available equipment (AGRITECH PROVIDER, ADVISOR, FARMER). Moreover, there were a number of corresponding articles in the local agrarian press, Navarra Agraria (MEDIA).

Dissemination phase

While the same group of actors were involved well into the dissemination phase, both the technology distributors and farmers became more prominent (AGRITECH PROVIDER, FARMER). Whether or not new tractors have automatic guidance technology is decided upon their purchase, since it is an optional feature (FARMER, AGRITECH PROVIDER, AGRITECH MANUFACTURER). Technicians of ITG Agrícola-INTIA train and advise farmers, and therefore continue to have an important role in the dissemination of CTF (ADVISOR, FARMER). During this phase, the guidance systems in the tractor are continuously being simplified, better integrated into tractor functioning, and better connected to the RTK network and GPS signal (INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER). The Government of Navarre maintains the RTK network, which improves the coverage and accuracy of positioning based on the GPS signal (INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER). CTF is constantly improving in connectivity, is more user-friendly and is increasingly integrated into tractors, thereby reducing investment costs and increasing farm profitability. ITG Agrícola-INTIA continues to give presentations and demonstrations in the field (ADVISOR, FARMER).

Key attributes, drivers and hindrances

The collaboration between innovative companies and their distributors, public administration, farmers and technicians in ITG Agrícola-INTIA was key to the initial innovation process success. ITG Agrícola-INTIA had an important role as a mediator between the different actor groups. Peer-to-peer learning between farmers had a special role, because some of the farmers were practical experienced users. Technicians from ITG Agrícola-INTIA were important as advisors to farmers. The practicality, profitability, and advantages of the guidance system itself are essential to the innovation success. INTIA has acted as a facilitator and innovation broker, specifically by training and disseminating knowledge on CTF. The network of RTK stations set up by the Government of Navarre provides free positioning accuracy. Setting up these stations formed the basis for the new technology and improved accessibility for the machinery manufacturers. Companies have also shifted their emphasis towards providing advisory services and support for CTF implementation. The biggest barrier was and remains the cost of initial investment. Thus, the subsidies from the Government of Navarre target this issue by supporting GPS installation in tractors.

Table 7 Overview of the key drivers and hindrances in the CTF innovation process in Spain

CTF	Drivers	Hindrances
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> dissemination of technology through talks and demonstrations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cost of the equipment limited technological support from the technicians of the distribution companies

Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of accuracy in positioning that RTK network supposed • equipment is becoming cheaper and offers are reaching more professional users in agricultural sector • Distributors of companies improving their knowledge of technology and offering better support services to farmers • Subsidies for Investment begin to be provided by regional administration of Navarra • ITG Agrícola-INTIA continued with dissemination of advantages and difficulties of technology through meetings, seminars, demonstrations and publications (personalized advice of technical specialists of ITG Agrícola-INTIA widely used by farmers, who greatly appreciate their expert, independent, timely and close contribution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • costs and profitability of the investment (especially for medium and small farms, only for largest farms investment is profitable at the beginning)
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • farmer discovers improvement that guiding brings in comfort and quality of his work on tractor (allows working with reduced visibility) and contribution to precision of agricultural work • access of young people to farms • installation of new irrigation systems and modernization of irrigation facilities in Navarra makes it necessary to work with greater precision - introduction of GPS and Guidance • Investment subsidies from the regional government of Navarra • ITG Agrícola-INTIA continues training, disseminating and advising 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • investment cost for medium and small farms (some cooperatives of common use of machinery (CUMA'S), cooperatives of production in common and service providers appear as the alternative for these small farms)

3.6 Controlled Traffic Farming (with permanent traffic lanes) (UK)

Innovation Profile

Controlled traffic farming (CTF) reduces soil compaction to narrow strips across fields and maximizes the area of undamaged soil for cropping by matching machinery tracks. This is facilitated by satellite based auto-guidance with RTK correction to be +/-2 cm accuracy

although in the early days it used or with conventional marking systems (CTF website). In UK and elsewhere particularly in Northern Europe CTF describes a system of using permanent traffic lanes, used for all field operations and, with RTK, are able to be used permanently, year after year leading to friable, easily cultivated soils suitable for minimum tillage.

Innovation process and timeline

Figure 9 Graphical timeline of the innovation process of CTF in the UK

Initiation phase

In the 1980s, agricultural soil compaction became a visible problem to researchers. CTF offered a solution by reducing the area of compacted soils parallel to saving on costs related to tillage and soil health inputs. However, CTF was not widely adopted , although use of RTK corrected auto-guidance was widely used for individual growing seasons, due to incompatible machinery, lacking visual impact (observability) and machinery guidance systems. An independent advisor (ADVISOR) was working to change agricultural mechanisation so it would not compact soil. The project received an “Exploratory Award” from the EU (MEDIA, PUBLIC AUTHORITY). Thereafter the advisor gave a presentation about CTF to Unilever’s global food production team (AGRI-TECH PROVIDER), and they provided a demonstration field at their UK site. A large American machinery company (AGRI-TECH MANUFACTURER) provided a combine harvester and specialized tractor, both equipped with a global navigation satellite system (GNSS) and auto-steer. A seed drill from a UK company (AGRI-TECH MANUFACTURER) was integrated into the machinery and the project started in 2004. A small farmer-focus group (FARMER) was developed to oversee the project, and Unilever (PRIVATE FUNDING ORGANIZATION) provided funds to manage and promote the demonstration. The advisor (ADVISOR) consequently gave more talks on CTF

and publicised the CTF demonstration on the Unilever farm (MEDIA). The latter stimulated interest and was enhanced by a short video taken on the site and shown at presentations (MEDIA). In addition, the advisor sought funds from the Douglas Bomford Trust (PRIVATE FUNDING ORGANIZATION), to give more talks on the benefits of CTF around the UK. In 2008 both the machinery and the GNSS signal were changed to be more CTF-appropriate. The GNSS company (INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER) offered an upgrade to a ground-based or RTK correction signal, which improved the signal so that it could be used for auto steering. Workshops were held on the Unilever site, and one or two of the focus group farmers showed interest or made their first attempts to adopt CTF, on their farms as well (FARMERS). These early meetings attracted between 15 and 20 people and prompted a web-based membership scheme (PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION), for which there was an annual fee. Members were circulated workshop details and provided with reports following the workshops, occurring throughout Europe mostly under the umbrella of the International Soil Tillage Research Organisation (ISTRO) and its CTF Working Group (PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION). Outreach to potential partners was welcomed by GNSS providers (INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER) who saw CTF as a means of selling more of their products (MARKETER). Machinery suppliers (AGRITECH PROVIDER) at this stage were more difficult to attract because few, if any, had machines that had been customised to CTF. There were a number of publications and presentations to made available to research, practice, and industry by 2010 (MEDIA).

Implementation Phase

After 5 years of the CTF project, there were more than 500 members in the CTF group (PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION), and CTF was getting attention beyond the CTF group. A group of farmers (FARMERS) set up demo farms that used CTF. There was growing coverage of CTF in the farming press (MEDIA) and case studies were presented on the CTF website. Workshops continued on a regular basis and attendance doubled. 2015 there was an international conference on CTF in Prague (FARMERS, PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION, AGRITECH MANUFACTURER, AGRITECH PROVIDER, INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER). There was a field visit to a large demo farm using CTF (AGRITECH PROVIDER).

Dissemination Phase

CTF with permanent traffic-lanes is not yet acknowledged as a solution to combatting agricultural soil compaction, and it is rarely recommended by advisors (ADVISOR). However, farmers who adopt CTF are promoting it among their peers (FARMER).

Key attributes, drivers and hindrances

The private advisor was key to starting demonstration farms and the CTF farmer network. Large corporate sponsors made the demonstration of the technology possible. In this case study, farmer-to-farmer networks of information, combined with field demonstrations of CTF were and continue to be crucial in further dissemination of the innovation. The private advisor was central to the formation of the farmer focus group and the network of information. Moreover, the large corporate sponsors of field and machinery in the implementation phase were instrumental to initiate the use of CTF.

Table 8 Overview of the key drivers and hindrances in each phase of the CTF innovation process in the UK.

CTF	Drivers	Hindrances
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> dissemination of technology through talks and demonstrations farmer focus group demonstration farm large corporate sponsors multiplication of demonstration farms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> incompatibility of equipment lack of funding demonstration farms
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> farmer membership of CTF focus group grew workshops on demonstration farms continued case studies of CTF on farms were produced press coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sponsorship/funding
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> demonstration farms continued talks and presentations by advisor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of information and spread of knowledge amongst farmers/farmers try to circumvent using the CTF

4 Results

We received six case studies on successful innovation processes. After a first review of the cases, we grouped them in two categories: innovative products and innovative practices. Three cases were innovative products, which were developed in about the past five years, whereas the remaining three cases were innovative agricultural practices made possible by preceding technologies (GPS, automation), and were developed in the course of the past 20 years. Here, we first present key actors from each case study, and then summarize the key supporting and hindering factors in each innovation phase in each of the categories.

4.1 Key Actors

We identified 14 actors that came up during the case studies. Some of the actors had different functions, depending on the innovation phase in which they were active, or due to different activities occurring during a single innovation phase. When looking at the key actors as listed in each of the innovation phases, there are several trends that are noticeable. In all case studies, farmers were involved in the innovation process during all phases. In several case studies, farmers were mentioned more than once in each phase. This is largely due to the many different functions that farmers had in the different innovation case studies. In the initiation phases, farmers were often collaborators, in the sense that they advised the innovator on which characteristics would be important for the innovation. In innovative products, farmers trained the innovators, in order for the innovators to understand farming. In some cases, they tested the innovations at the beginning. In several cases, farmers were the end-users. Advisors and professional associations both assumed different functions at different phases and depending on the innovation. Funding organizations were

key actors in several innovations, but were public (i.e. EU), private (i.e. trusts), or venture capital.

In the innovative products, IT experts were instrumental to developing the innovation, whereas in the innovative practices, agri-tech manufacturers and providers were frequently listed as providing the tools, the fields, or funds. In these cases, the manufacturers and providers had different functions, as they hosted or sponsored the demonstrations, acted as funding organizations, or provided technology for demonstrations. Manufacturers had to produce the technologies so that they were compatible with the practices, for example adapting tractor width. Manufacturers also functioned as sponsors of the technology adoption by providing the appropriate technology and fields for demonstrations. Moreover, in the innovative practice cases, infrastructure providers were instrumental to the innovation processes. Infrastructure made the technologies possible in the first place. Public authorities had the role of passing legislation that made the technology more relevant, and thereby fostered adoption, also through subsidies (Table 9).

Table 9 The number of times actors were mentioned in each case innovation phase in each case study.

	Case 1 - trecker.com			Case 2 - agrivi			Case 3 - arable smart sprayer			Case 4- section control in spraying			Case 5- CTF Spain			Case 6 - CTF UK			
	Initiation	Implementation	Dissemination	Initiation	Implementation	Dissemination	Initiation	Implementation	Dissemination	Initiation	Implementation	Dissemination	Initiation	Implementation	Dissemination	Initiation	Implementation	Dissemination	
Farmer	4	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1
Researcher							1	1		1									
Advisor				1			1	1			1		4	2	1	2			1
IT expert	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1											
Competitor			1																
Marketer						2												1	
Media			2											1		3	1		
Professional association			1	1			1	1	1				1	1		3	2		
Funding organization		1	1		3	1							1			3	1		
Public authority					1					1		1	2	1					
Infrastructure provider										1				1	2	2	1		
Agri-tech manufacturer											2	2	1	2	2	1	4	1	
Agri-tech provider											1	1	1	3	2	2	1	1	
Private Actor	1																		

4.2 Innovative products

We categorized trecker.com (GER), Agrivi (CRO/SER), and the arable smart sprayer app (ASSA) (GR) as innovative products. As ASSA was still in the first phase of the diffusion process at the time of the case study, less detailed information was available and we focused the comparative view on the first two products. We complement our findings with ASSA when possible.

Initiation phase – supporting and hindering factors

In both management apps (trecker.com and agrivi), the founders' IT knowledge and personality were important. It was remarkable that neither of them had a background in agriculture, but immersed themselves in it (starting own production and working for farms) to gain agronomic knowledge. Although this lacking knowledge could be considered a hindering factor, it ended up being a supporting factor, as the founders had a fresh view on the problems to solve and were highly motivated to cooperate with farmers and contractors to gain hands-on knowledge. In the case of ASSA, cooperation between the founder (IT-expert and researchers) and farmer cooperative was a key supporting factor for initiating the innovation. Funding was no major issue for the innovators in the initiation phase as they were able to pay costs for their own resources.

Implementation phase – supporting and hindering factors

With the innovation processes moving forward, the required inputs (human and financial resources) increased significantly. Specifically in the cases of trecker.com and agrivi, new actors came on board with their investments. Similarly, both apps won a number of awards and thereby gained publicity and attention. Subsequently, innovators intensified their efforts to mobilize additional funds e.g. through financial support of investors or trophy money. ASSA benefited through little competition and high demand for their app.

Dissemination phase – supporting and hindering factors

For their product dissemination, trecker.com is working to spread with the next generation of farmers (end users) via contact to universities, and agrivi is trying to spread into new markets by connecting with larger suppliers and industry partners who reach relevant end users through other channels. Trecker.com was supported in the dissemination phase through EU funding (Big Data Agrarplattform, 2017) and by being part of an entrepreneurs' organization (<http://www.eogermany.com/>), which can provide support in their development. Agrivi was supported in the dissemination phase through EU training for capacity building (Ready2Go project). ASSA is being fine-tuned and during this process is trying to break out beyond the initial farmers' cooperatives to reach more farmers.

4.3 Innovative technology driven practices

We categorized automatic guiding of agricultural machinery (ES), section control on sprayers with use of GPS (NL) and Controlled Traffic Farming using permanent traffic-lanes (UK) as innovative technology driven practices. This category of innovations had less clearly defined phases in their development – initiation, implementation, and dissemination phases overlap. We think this is the case because the fine-tuning and development of these innovations is a continuous process of adaptation.

Initiation phase – supporting and hindering factors

The initiative for the development of the innovative practices – in all three cases – seemed to come most dominantly from a combination of supporting factors. In the last couple decades, many technological options became available and the infrastructure was increasingly ready. This readiness, combined with farmers' experimentation with CTF made these types of technology-driven practices possible. Farm machinery companies and (public) research organizations were key actors in facilitating farmers' observation and experimentation with CTF and section control. A second important driver was national public interest as expressed by regulations. Important supporting actors in these cases are public advisory services (e.g. ITG Agrícola-INTIA, ES-case), CTF networks for farmers and industry (professional associations), and advisory services (e.g. Delphy). Key supporting events in these cases included field demonstrations and information provision from the very beginning of the innovation process. Another aspect mentioned in two of the three cases is the appearance of the subject in European projects (CTF and section control). Lack of funding for workshops or demonstrations were hindering the innovation at given points. Furthermore, incompatibility of equipment and limited technological support were mentioned as the main hindering factors in this phase.

Implementation phase – supporting and hindering factors

The main supporting factor of the implementation phase was information support. Specifically, field demonstrations and seminars by advisors and agri-tech manufacturers and providers companies for farmers and other relevant stakeholders were an important supporting factor. Further factors in support of the innovative technology driven practices included media coverage, the training of technicians by companies for better advice regarding the new technology, and a growing membership of the controlled traffic farming network membership. To tackle the mistrust towards the new practice, farmer-to-farmer communication (e.g. demonstrations on private farms of the innovative practice) was named as an important instrument. In the implementation phase, the lack of funding for workshops and demonstrations was still one of the major hindering factors. Besides the mistrust in the technology itself, the costs and the profitability of the investment made by farmers impede the innovation process.

Dissemination phase – supporting and hindering factors

In the dissemination phase, the benefits of the innovative practice seemed to be clearer to the farmers, in part due to farmer-to-farmer communication (e.g. CTF in the UK). Also, the information support and diffusion systems were still playing a decisive role in this phase, e.g. promotion by companies, farm journals, training by associations. The development of a greater variety of equipment was also overcoming hindering factors. The investment costs, in particular for small farms, were considered a hindering factor although the case studies reported the onset of national and regional subsidies (e.g. Navarre subsidies for investing in CTF technology in tractors) in support of the new practices.

5 Discussion

5.1 Key similarities between innovation types: actors and their interactions

Social interactions, specifically including cooperation and networking between actors was crucial to the success of the innovations we presented here, both the innovative practices and the innovative products. As demonstrated by the innovative products, the social interactions between the IT-specialists and farmers built knowledge that led to the innovation. Networking through professional associations played a large role for the practice innovations, since this strengthened peer-to-peer learning and support. Such collective behaviour can be addressed as social learning processes (Jiggins and Röling, 2000). Taking this into account, actors can work together to adapt innovations to their needs despite differing experiences and views, as shaped by the larger environment (van Bommel et al., 2009). We assume that such integrative and cross-boundary co-adaption contributed to the success of innovative products. Similarly, farmer-to-farmer networks that may also include other key actors (e.g. CTF organizations) were strengthened through the important role of demonstrations for disseminating information or innovations. In such cases, the trialability and observability characteristics of innovations were influential for their adoption. In the demonstration atmosphere and exchange among actors, trust issues become non-issues. This can be explained by the positive aspect of demonstrations largely being removed from other struggles and an “atmosphere of trust” where the views and knowledge of all present actors are considered equally, thereby enabling social learning processes to occur (Schneider et al., 2009).

5.2 Key differences between innovation types

There were a few key differences between the two innovation types. The product innovations that we studied here span between 3 and 6 years, while the innovative practices developed (and continue to do so) over the course of 15 to 30 years. In the innovative products, the main innovators were the IT-experts. In the case of the innovative practices, the innovator is not so easily and unequivocally identifiable. The innovative practices describe the application of the technologies, which evolved over the course of the time. The innovator may have been the individual actor who propagated the practice (e.g. in the UK case, the “independent advisor”), or individual actors at different times. Since the practice is not about a single technology or single product, it is hard to identify the exact origin. The innovative products can all be classified as IT innovations and here, IT experts were mostly the innovators themselves who predominantly cooperated with farmers and farmers’ associations and throughout all phases. Funding organisations were important, while other actors appeared only in single phases and in few numbers. In contrast, the actors involved in all phases of the innovative practices are more numerous and more diverse. Agritech providers were important actors and equally, advisors played a more important role. These differences of actors involved in the different innovation types can be clearly linked to the character of the innovations.

5.3 Environmental factors affecting innovation processes

Environmental factors that influenced the innovation case studies include policies, natural conditions, and a socio-technical regime, which is a term that describes the place in which established practices and associated rules exist that make systems stable (Darnhofer, 2015).

The structural perspective (Fig. 1) on innovations provides a useful lens in which to explore the innovative practices. This could be due to the development of these innovations, and iterative socio-technical changes that occur over time. Innovative practices were very much shaped and spurred by policy changes (e.g. chemical drift in surface waters in the Netherlands, farming subsidies in Navarre) and natural conditions (e.g. soil compaction as recognized problem on farms in the UK and in the CTF association). However, using the dynamic perspective (Fig. 2) could also explain the development of the innovative practices, since these innovations provide a longer timeframe for observing the innovation process, and identifying the points in time in which changes were triggered or new dynamics evolved. Decisive points in time were the collaborations between key actors that were also location, technology, and practice specific, and depended very much on the “socio-technical regime.” The change in the British socio-technical regime, for example, was facilitated by the realization throughout the agricultural research sector that uncontrolled soil compaction is not conducive to a sustainable agricultural production. The larger environmental factors affecting innovative products may be at the larger socio-technical landscape, which is undergoing digitization at large, and which in turn benefit the diffusion of apps and software throughout a broader spectrum of end-users.

5.4 Lessons for successful innovations

The product and practice innovations faced a different pallet of fostering and hindering factors and different actors. Specifically, the innovative products were hindered exclusively by funding, while the innovative practices faced a wider variety of hindrances (e.g. funding, technical hurdles, infrastructural issues). Although the two groups of innovations have very different characteristics, in both cases, intense collaboration with end-users (farmers) made the innovations relevant. The two groups of successful innovations were dependent on funding at the right time during the innovation process. Funding was connected with project grants, federal subsidies, IT Start-Up awards/competitions, NGOs, or large corporate sponsors. Government regulations regarding environmental thresholds and standards were instrumental in SFT development for establishing the core requirements of the “socio-technical regime.”

“Soft systems” thinking emphasizes the role of different factors that constitute the social constructs governing interactions between actors (Darnhofer et al., 2012). Here, these factors were more related to communication and value types (“openness” of developers of *trecker.com*) of innovators. For example, developers of the apps and software were IT-experts and had no in-depth knowledge of agriculture. They relied on other actors (farmers, researchers, private actors), the cooperation with them and the feedback from them. With their fresh view, they sincerely listened to farmers’ needs. Their high motivation was a crucial supporting factor that encouraged the innovators to seek out collaborations with other actors, specifically with farmers.

The case studies we presented here provide examples for a number of factors that pave the way for success of the innovations. For example, the case studies show that demonstrations can provide evidence that innovations works. Moreover, professional associations and demonstrations provided educational input to the farmers as end-users by transferring information regarding GPS during training. Lack of competition is a benefit for innovations, if they are filling a niche that is not otherwise addressed in any way. Infrastructural changes through improvement of the GPS signal (RTK stations), environmental legislation (chemical drift issue in The Netherlands) or farm management (irrigation example in Spain) further will

create an environment where the agricultural sector is prepared for and open to innovations. Since innovations are place or context specific, it is hard to prescribe the environment in which they best fit. Instead, successful innovations respond to and take advantage of the larger environment or environmental changes, available actors, and funding to shape the innovation so it works. Besides individual motivation, other soft factors like the innovators' positive attitudes (trecker.com, agrivi) or endurance (CTF in both UK and Spain) are potentially essential factors that can guarantee success and ensure that the innovation can respond to end-user needs appropriately.

5. 5 Reflections on the methodology

Our case studies were successful, and in being successful, overcame hurdles, or used hurdles as lessons to further their success. In other words, the innovators turned challenges (e.g. infrastructural or technological readiness'), into opportunities. Thus, hindering factors were not so well portrayed in these innovation case studies. However, we would assume that if everything that *did* work well, did not work, then it would be a hindering factor. We would have to conduct an ex-post analysis with innovations that were not successful in order to find out more.

Considering the case studies and data collection, we conclude that comprehensive training, to the extent that we conducted it, was essential for project partners in charge of and conducting the case studies. Nevertheless, we learned that the necessary involvement of practitioners and companies for gathering information holds risks (delays, hindrances, or even complete cancellation of case studies). It should be respected also, that despite risks, actors not originally working in research but participating in scientific processes, invested a noticeable amount of time and resources without knowing whether their effort would result in proportional learning benefits for themselves or for the innovations they studied.

Lastly, after receiving the case study reports, it was clear that it the varying quality of information, quantity of information, and how in-depth the project partners went (or were able to) hindered comparative analyses between cases.

6 Conclusions and recommendations

From the presented case studies, we conclude that working in close cooperation with farmers throughout all innovation phases is a strong supporting factor for successful processes and can be recommended to all other actors interested in SFT innovation. In contrast, in our cases we didn't find the example of a farmer's driven SFT innovation which might indicate the complexity associated with digitization and many other perceived hurdles in the case of SFT in general (Kernecker et al. 2016). However, innovations can only be relevant to farmers if they reflect farmers' needs and correspond to the larger environment their farms are in.

Secondly, it seems that the divide in the technological complexity and the degree of required learning and change of farmers' practices as expressed through the two categories 'innovative product' and 'innovation practice' could constitute a major guiding difference ('Leitdifferenz'), in particular to discern how SFT – other types of innovations – can contribute to agricultural sustainability. Further research is necessary to substantiate this assumption.

Although the inspected cases are very instructive with regard to key actors, driving and hindering factors, and specific characteristics related to SFT innovations, they do not allow

for conclusions that go far beyond due to their singularities. However, they provide an excellent base from which to formulate more specific research questions and to focus study categories on digital innovations in agriculture. Thus, we encourage a more in-depth exploration of the role of field days and demonstrations for innovative practices to underline the strength of the innovation characteristic “observability” for its success. Also, the question of costs and funding did arise at different points as one of the main hindering factors for both the development of the innovation process and the adoption of SFT. In this regard, analysing the impact of investors, government aids and other funding sources/financial support is one interesting aspect to focus on further. More research would be necessary to more critically assess which types of funding would be crucial at which point, and how they could benefit certain actor constellations at those points. Another hurdle for each of the innovative processes was infrastructure – specifically GPS, and RTK and technological development (CTF and section control). CTF and section control could only be developed after GPS became established, reflecting a long period of development, which was greatly supported by the agri-tech industry (demonstrations, demo farms, technology sponsorship, conferences), and would not have been possible without them, given the high costs associated with the innovation process, compared to the costs of developing apps and software.

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Annex I Profile pattern

Title/Name of innovation

Innovation Profile

to be filled for each proposal

Country:	
Contact:	Farmer(s), user(s) of innovation Name & Address
Proposal by:	
Research tandem:	
Case conductor/ team:	
Source:	<input type="checkbox"/> Online Inventory <input type="checkbox"/> RIW <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Type of SFT/innovation:	<input type="checkbox"/> Agricultural app <input type="checkbox"/> Drones, mapping, aerial imagery <input type="checkbox"/> Robots, autonomous machines <input type="checkbox"/> GPS, controlled traffic, VRT etc. <input type="checkbox"/> weather, soil moisture sensor with automatic data upload <input type="checkbox"/> Network/cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Hardware & machinery <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Est. number of current users/beneficiaries:	
Interest of stakehold- ers to participate	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>

Short description:

- **Name of innovation**
- **Key features and functionality**
- **State of development/diffusion** (*prototype - only applied in test situations / first phase of diffusion process - there are only a few early innovators, making use of the innovation in practice / second or third phase of the diffusion process - several or many people are already using the innovation*)
- **Actors involved** in the course of the (especially early) innovation development process (e.g. advisors, private firms, public research bodies and universities, experimental stations, financial service providers, others etc....)

Impact:

e.g.

- **Economic benefits** for the farmer (reduction of costs, yield quality)
- **Environment** (soil quality, water pollution, water use)
- **Biodiversity** in the farmed environment
- Improvement of **animal / plant health**
- Development of **rural economy** (new business opportunities e.g. use of biomasses, bioenergy production)

Data availability:

e.g. publications, documentation etc.

Annex II Assessment scheme

Title/Name of innovation

Assessment scheme

to be filled by selection premium members only

Country

- France Germany Greece Serbia Spain Netherlands the UK
 Other:

Type of innovation

- Agricultural app Drones, mapping, aerial imagery Robots, autonomous machines
 weather, soil moisture sensor with automatic data upload GPS, controlled traffic, VRT etc.
 Network/cooperative Hardware & machinery Other:

Selection criteria:

	YES	NO
Interest of stakeholders in publicity/networking		
Research tandem available		
More than one user/beneficiary		
More than two actors involved (advisors, firms et.c)		
Impact		
State of development/diffusion		
Prototype		
First phase of diffusion process		
Second or third phase of the diffusion process		
Data available and accessible		
Interest of stakeholders to participate		

Comment:

Selection recommended:

YES NO